

USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN GETTING PRIMARY CLASS PUPILS INTERESTED IN BADMINTON

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Abstract. *The article contains information about the history of the emergence of the game of badminton in the world community, the theoretical views of foreign scientists. Theoretical and practical foundations of junior schoolchildren's interest in badminton are highlighted.*

Keywords: *badminton, shuttlecock, ball, physical development, level, ability, mental, functional, complex, exercise, movement.*

Physical education and sports are recognized as an important factor of personality formation on a global scale. In fact, the theory of physical education is scientifically based on its content and essence, classification (tools, application processes) by experts in the field. Badminton sport is one of them, and its creation includes long periods.

Developing spiritual, artistic and moral culture of elementary school students, developing creative skills, artistic and aesthetic taste, directing them to professions, becoming physically fit and following a healthy lifestyle, education in the spirit of patriotism and training for military service, development of life skills is of great importance.

In the process of studying the relevance of our research, we referred to historical sources and managed to analyze the following information. Medieval English engravings depict peasants raising the wheel to each other. Images in historical photos of the 18th century show that people played a similar game in Russia at that time. Gavriil Derzhavin also wrote about the feather ball. In 1650, Queen Christina of Sweden built a special court near the Royal Palace in Stockholm to play "feather ball" with court ladies and foreign guests. This court is still preserved in the capital of Sweden and today it is the property of the church.

In England in the 19th century, the game of the wheel became very popular in the Duke of Bedford's household. The duke was a patron of the Badminton Association. Today, the Front Hall, which he owns, houses a wonderful collection of old rackets and shuttlecocks.

In 1860, Isaac Spratt wrote a book about badminton and described the first rules of this game. Homeland of modern badminton is India. It originated from a game that became popular in India in the 19th century and was called "pune" according to some sources, "roopa" according to others.

1957 can be recognized as the "birthday" of former "Union" badminton. From that day, badminton began to become popular in Moscow and Leningrad and some "Allied" republics. In 1962, unofficial competitions were organized between a number of republics (Russia, Ukraine, Belarus, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan), including the national teams of the cities of Moscow and Leningrad [1; 137 p.].

In China, the sport of badminton appeared as a form of physical activity of the people, that is, a game. The people of Szino used to shoot balls made of chicken feathers. The rules of playing it are similar to the sport of badminton today. During the game, the participants of both sides shoot the ball with their hands, the playing field is divided into two parts by a line. Participants of the first group throw the ball, and the second group returns it [3; pp. 11-12].

Even now, badminton is a popular and widespread sport in the People's Republic of China, and

serves as a means of developing children's physical and mental abilities, as well as functional status (Tang Wei, 2013; Zhu Rui, 2016; Zhang. Cheng, 2017). Public surveys conducted by Chinese scientists have shown that nearly half of elementary school students prefer playing badminton to other sports (Jia Jiechen 2011). Therefore, by introducing extracurricular activities using this sports game, it is possible to increase the indicators of physical development and readiness of children of junior school age. This type of sport is also an important factor in the development of the system of extracurricular activities. The main goal set by the leadership of the government is to attract citizens to physical education and sports throughout their lives and to protect the health of the nation. Badminton sport has various effects on the body of students, develops physical qualities, expands the arsenal of actions, strengthens willpower.

The national team of Uzbekistan took part in the former "Union" championship, held for the first time in 1963, and managed to take 9th place out of 14 teams. Since these years, badminton has rapidly developed and gained popularity in our country, especially in the cities of Tashkent, Fergana, Andijan, Navoi and Angren. In 1982, individual and team competitions of the former "Ittifak" badminton championship were held in Tashkent. In 1992 and 1995, international tournaments were organized for the first time in Tashkent. In 1998, the junior badminton team of the Republic of Uzbekistan participated in the Asian junior championship. In 1999, the national team of the Republic of Uzbekistan participated in the Asian Championship held in Kuala Lumpur and failed to advance beyond the qualifying tournament stage.

Wang Lin determined the theoretical foundations and practical ways of increasing the level of physical development of elementary school students, based on the role and place of intensive training methods by using exercises specific to playing badminton [2]. learning badminton as a sport in high school was not enough, therefore, the inclusion of this sport in the primary school curriculum not only lays the ground for the development of badminton as a sport, but also the formation of a pool of talented athletes and the training of physical education teachers "is an additional tool that allows to effectively direct the healthy development and physical fitness of students" [2].

According to anthropometric indicators and the vital capacity of the lungs, there are no statistically significant differences between boys and girls of elementary school students, which makes the classes organizationally and methodologically without distinction by gender. allows to build. Children's body mass and body mass index indicators have the same exact statistical correlation as physical fitness indicators. This implies the possibility of correcting body mass using methods based on the use of sports characterized by increased physical and emotional intensity. In order to implement the physical education program in the weekly training schedule, the high school program should include two physical education activities, therefore, the introduction of tools specific to the game of badminton, in which the proportion of total volume and high intensity need to increase [5; 5–6 b]. The importance of sports training at the initial stage of training badminton players is determined by the fact that the foundation for the sports training of young badminton players is laid in this period, and the mistakes made at this stage are difficult to correct later in the training process. This situation is more evident in the technique of game movements, which determines the main content of badminton player's training and competition activities.

Chan Duk Nyan (2013) said that with children achieving high results in badminton, maximum mobilization of all functional systems of the body is achieved. Sha Haisya, after a twelve-month badminton course at universities, found that badminton significantly contributed to

increasing muscle mass in boys and reducing body fat in girls, while hand grip strength increased. 'indicators have improved, muscles have increased, the shoulder girdle has been strengthened, and significant positive changes are observed in the correct breathing function of the body. The movements used in badminton are elementary and are based on exercises such as running, throwing, and jumping. This type of sport can be called not only a factor of physical development, but also an active recreation tool that relieves children of mental stress.

M.Tashtarian's research work is focused on the application of computer technologies in the training of young hearing impaired badminton players. Due to the complex effect of badminton equipment, metabolism and the functioning of the whole body improves, it activates the work of blood circulation and respiratory organs, and strengthens the nervous system. An experimental method aimed at increasing the level of physical development and physical fitness of young schoolchildren, using the game of badminton, involves increasing the volume of children's normalized movement activity by 50% and the intensity by 21% [7; 67-68 p].

Badminton helps elementary school students (grades 3-4) to develop personal qualities such as courage, self-confidence, quick thinking and observation, resourcefulness, and determination.

A.A. Gujalovsky (1986) O.V. Zhbankov (2000) K.B. Ilkevich (1998) V.D. Medvedkov (1999) developed a method of playing badminton to eliminate excess weight in 7-8-year-old children. In our opinion, the inclusion of badminton in the curriculum of primary classes will be a chain to ensure unity. That is, the effective functioning of students in general secondary education and vocational schools, higher educational institutions, increasing their intellectual potential, mass physical development of the nation, forming a healthy lifestyle, preparing for military service, helps to solve the problems of mental and physical development.

Based on the analysis of scientific and methodical literature and our preliminary research, it has been shown that it is necessary to determine the directions of optimizing the physical education of junior schoolchildren using the game of badminton.

A study conducted by Liu Fan showed that twice a week badminton training had a significant effect on weight loss; improving physical function and physical condition in middle-aged men; It has been proven that it has a positive effect on improving the state of mind, perception, and increasing the feeling of satisfaction [5; pp. 7–102]. The simplicity and convenience of badminton makes it possible for people of any age and gender to start playing this sport. Because this sport develops the skills of relying more on fast movement of arms and legs and running movements.

The sports achievements of Russian badminton players in the international arena took high places. They are winning Olympic medals, victories at the European Championships and World Cup stages, and prize-winning places at the World Universiade. Badminton does not overload the students, on the contrary, it provides an opportunity to play in the open air on simple courts. Also, badminton is a technically complex game. High-class athletes move quickly and easily from one end of the field to the other, and do not allow the shuttlecock to fall on the field in difficult situations. Therefore, badminton players are always faced with intellectual and motor tasks, which they solve during the game. So, getting elementary school students interested in badminton ensures that they grow up mature in all aspects. In 3rd-4th grade students, there is a correlation between forming the basis of various movements and mastering the technical elements of badminton.

In the national curriculum of physical education of general secondary education, 3rd graders have information on aesthetic culture and creative competence, focusing on the phases of hand and foot conditions. In terms of self-development and self-care competence, follows the procedure of correct leg movements during short-distance running, students should have theoretical knowledge about exercises such as walking, running, jumping and throwing, defined. Badminton training is effective in raising the physical performance of elementary school students and improving their fitness. Badminton, as a form of fitness sport, develops physical qualities proportionately, includes training exercises for quickness, strength, flexibility, agility and endurance. The analysis of foreign and national experiences showed that it is necessary to teach badminton sport in the primary grades of general secondary education (grades 3-4).

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